

FEATURES OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF MANIC AND MIXED EPISODES IN PATIENTS WITH BIPOLAR AFFECTIVE DISORDER UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF CANNABINOIDS

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ANNOTATION: Relevance. The use of cannabinoids significantly affects the course of bipolar affective disorder (BAD). In particular, the pathoplastic effect on the development of the first manic or mixed episode has been insufficiently studied in the scientific literature. Moreover, the lack of unified diagnostic criteria for mixed manic states creates challenges in clinical practice. Objective. The aim of the study was to identify the characteristics of the first manic or mixed episode in patients with bipolar affective disorder under the influence of cannabinoids and to investigate potential predictors of euthymia formation. Materials and Methods. The study included 47 patients diagnosed with bipolar affective disorder (manic or mixed episode) during their first hospitalization. Patients were divided into two groups: 1) 26 patients (17 men, 9 women) with cannabinoid dependence; 2) 21 patients (16 men, 5 women) in the control group who did not use cannabinoids. Syndromic, symptomatic, and functional recovery, as well as hospitalization duration and treatment adherence, were evaluated. Results. Among cannabinoid users, manic episodes with psychotic symptoms were more common (45%), while mixed episodes predominantly manifested with anxiety symptoms (34%). In the control group, 92% of patients achieved symptomatic recovery, compared to only 37% in the cannabinoid-dependent group. Cannabinoid users had longer hospital stays and lower adherence to treatment. Additionally, they more frequently experienced manic syndrome with psychotic features. Conclusion. Cannabinoid use in patients with bipolar affective disorder contributes to frequent recurrence of episodes, poor treatment adherence, and reduced functional performance during euthymia. Psychotic symptoms are more prominent in the structure of manic syndrome, while mixed manic episodes often present as dysphoric mania. Analysis of the data allowed the identification of two clinical variants of bipolar affective disorder: the first variant is characterized by single or irregular, well-defined mixed manic episodes; the second variant features frequent recurrence of mixed manic episodes with minimal remission, associated with a less favorable prognosis.

Keywords: bipolar affective disorder, cannabinoids, manic episode, mixed episode, pathoplastic effect, euthymia, psychotic symptoms.

ОСОБЕННОСТИ РАЗВИТИЯ МАНИАКАЛЬНЫХ И СМЕШАННЫХ ЭПИЗODOB У БОЛЬНЫХ С БИПОЛЯРНЫМ АФФЕКТИВНЫМ РАССТРОЙСТВОМ ПОД ВОЗДЕЙСТВИЕМ КАННАБИНОИДОВ

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АННОТАЦИЯ: Актуальность. Использование каннабиноидов оказывает значительное влияние на течение биполярного аффективного расстройства (БАР). В частности, патопластическое воздействие на развитие первого маниакального или смешанного эпизода недостаточно изучено в научной литературе. Кроме того, отсутствие единых диагностических критериев для смешанных маниакальных состояний создает трудности в клинической практике. Цель. Цель исследования - выявить особенности первого маниакального или смешанного эпизода у пациентов с биполярным аффективным расстройством под воздействием каннабиноидов и изучить потенциальные предикторы формирования эутимии. Материалы и методы. В исследование были включены 47 пациентов с диагнозом биполярного аффективного расстройства (маниакальный или смешанный эпизод) во время первой госпитализации. Пациенты были разделены на две группы: 1) 26 пациентов (17 мужчин, 9 женщин) с зависимостью от каннабиноидов; 2) 21 пациент (16 мужчин, 5 женщин) в контрольной группе, не использующие каннабиноиды. Оценивались синдромное, симптоматическое и функциональное восстановление, продолжительность госпитализации и приверженность лечению. Результаты. Среди употребляющих каннабиноиды маниакальные эпизоды с психотическими симптомами встречались чаще (45%), а смешанные эпизоды преимущественно проявлялись симптомами тревожности (34%). В контрольной группе 92% пациентов достигли симптоматического восстановления, в то время как в группе с зависимостью от каннабиноидов этот показатель составил лишь 37%. У пациентов, употребляющих каннабиноиды, наблюдалась более длительная госпитализация и низкая приверженность лечению. Кроме того, у них чаще встречался маниакальный синдром с психотическими симптомами. Выводы. Использование каннабиноидов у пациентов с биполярным аффективным расстройством способствует частому рецидиву эпизодов, низкой приверженности лечению и снижению функциональной активности в период эутимии. Психотические симптомы более выражены в структуре маниакального синдрома, а смешанные

маниакальные эпизоды часто проявляются в форме дисфорической мании. Анализ данных позволил выделить два клинических варианта течения БАР: первый вариант характеризуется единичными или нерегулярными, четко выраженными смешанными маниакальными эпизодами; второй вариант - частые рецидивы смешанных маниакальных эпизодов с минимальными периодами ремиссии, что связано с менее благоприятным прогнозом.

Ключевые слова: биполярное аффективное расстройство, каннабиноиды, маниакальный эпизод, смешанный эпизод, патопластический эффект, эутимия, психотические симптомы.

KANNABINOID TA'SIRIDA BIPOLYAR AFFEKTIV BUZILISHLI BEMORLARDA MANIAKAL VA ARALASH EPIZODLARNING RIVOJLANISH XUSUSIYATLARI

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ANNOTATSIYA: Dolzarblik. Kannabinoidlardan foydalanish bipolyar affektiv buzilish (BAB) kechishiga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Ayniqsa, birinchi maniakal yoki aralash epizodning rivojlanishidagi pathoplastik effekt hali ilmiy adabiyotlarda yetarlicha o'rganilmagan. Shuningdek, aralash maniakal holatlarni aniqlashda diagnostik kriteriyalarning uyg'un emasligi klinik amaliyotda muammolar tug'diradi. Maqsad. Tadqiqotning maqsadi - kannabinoidlar ta'sirida bipolyar affektiv buzilishli bemorlarda birinchi maniakal yoki aralash epizodning rivojlanish xususiyatlarini aniqlash va eutimiya shakllanishining potentsial prediktorlarini o'rganish. Materiallar va usullar. Tadqiqotga birinchi hospitalizatsiya paytida bipolyar affektiv buzilish (maniakal yoki aralash epizod) tashxisi qo'yilgan 47 nafar bemor jalb qilindi. Bemorlar ikkita guruhga bo'lindi: 1) 26 bemor (17 erkak, 9 ayol) kannabinoidlarga bog'liq; 2) 21 bemor (16 erkak, 5 ayol) kannabinoidlardan foydalanmaydigan boshqaruv guruhi. Klinik va funksional tiklanish, simptomatik va sindromatik baholar, shuningdek, hospitalizatsiya davomiyligi va davolashga rioya qilish darajasi o'rganildi. Natijalar. Kannabinoidlardan foydalanuvchi bemorlarda maniakal epizodlar psixotik simptomlar bilan ko'proq kuzatildi (45%), aralash epizodlar esa asosan xavotir simptomlari bilan namoyon bo'ldi (34%). Boshqaruv guruhidagi bemorlarning 92% simptomatik tiklanishga erishgan bo'lsa, birinchi guruhda bu ko'rsatkich 37% ni tashkil qildi. Kannabinoid ishlatadigan bemorlarning hospitalizatsiya davomiyligi uzoqroq va davolashga rioya qilish darajasi past bo'ldi. Shuningdek, ular psixotik simptomlar bilan tavsiflanadigan maniakal sindromga ko'proq duch kelishdi. Xulosa. Kannabinoidlardan foydalanish bipolyar affektiv buzilishli bemorlarda epizodlarning tez-tez takrorlanishiga, davolashga kam rioya qilishga va eutimiya davrida past funksional samaradorlikka

olib keladi. Bunda psixotik simptomlar maniakal sindrom tarkibida ko‘proq uchraydi, aralash maniakal holatlar esa ko‘pincha disforik maniaga xos klinik ko‘rinishda namoyon bo‘ladi. Tahlil natijalari bipolyar affektiv buzilishning ikki klinik variantini ajratishga imkon berdi: birinchi variant - yagona yoki noaniq aralash maniak epizodlar, ikkinchisi - tez-tez takrorlanuvchi aralash maniak epizodlar bilan tavsiflanadi, bu esa kasallik oqimi uchun noqulay prognoz ko‘rsatkichidir.

Kalit so‘zlar: bipolyar affektiv buzilish, kannabinoidlar, maniakal epizod, aralash epizod, pathoplastik effekt, eutimiya, psixotik simptomlar.

Introduction. A significant body of research indicates that the clinical course of bipolar affective disorder (BAD) in individuals who begin using substances such as cannabinoids prior to their first affective episode tends to be less severe compared to patients who develop substance dependence after the onset of affective episodes [1]. Despite growing interest in the interplay between substance use and bipolar disorder, the pathoplastic impact of cannabinoids on the emergence of initial manic or mixed episodes has been insufficiently examined in the scientific literature [2].

A major challenge in both research and clinical practice is the lack of standardized diagnostic criteria for mixed manic states. As noted by Gupta, existing diagnostic frameworks show considerable variability in sensitivity. For example, in patients presenting with at least one depressive symptom during mania, the Vienna criteria identified 94% of mixed episodes, the Cincinnati criteria identified 78%, the Pisan criteria 53%, and the ICD-10 and DSM-IV criteria identified only 16% and 9%, respectively [3,4]. This inconsistency highlights the limitations of conventional classifications and underscores the need for more nuanced diagnostic approaches.

ICD-10 does not recognize mixed mania as a distinct diagnostic category, providing only general guidelines for identifying mixed affective episodes. Within this framework, a mixed episode is described as an affective episode lasting at least two weeks, characterized by the co-occurrence or rapid alternation of hypomanic, manic, and depressive symptoms. While these symptoms should be prominent for most of the episode, they may not fully reach the threshold for a formal syndromic diagnosis [5-8]. Similarly, the American DSM-IV classification previously required the simultaneous presence of manic and depressive symptoms on a near-daily basis for at least one week to diagnose a “mixed episode,” which effectively limited the identification of mixed states in clinical practice.

In recent decades, attempts to broaden the conceptualization of mixed states are reflected in the DSM-5, which replaced DSM-IV [9]. DSM-5 represents a paradigm shift by reframing mixed features as an additional specifier of manic or hypomanic episodes, rather than a standalone category. According to DSM-5, a manic or hypomanic episode qualifies as having “mixed features” if at least three depressive symptoms are present nearly every day during a manic episode of at least one week, or a hypomanic episode lasting four days. This reclassification effectively positions mixed states as secondary characteristics of affective episodes rather than independent nosological entities [10–12].

Despite these adjustments, this approach has been criticized for underestimating the independent clinical significance of mixed states [13]. Epidemiological studies indicate that mixed mania is relatively common in patients with bipolar disorder. For instance, Vieta et al. reported that the prevalence of mixed manic episodes among hospitalized patients was 12.9% according to DSM-IV-TR, 9% per ICD-10, 16.7% per McElroy criteria, and up to 23.2% on clinical evaluation [14,15]. González-Pinto and colleagues found

that approximately one-third of patients with bipolar disorder experience mixed manic episodes during their lifetime [16].

Mixed mania is frequently associated with more severe disease courses, poorer prognoses, and higher rates of suicidality compared to pure mania [17–19]. Therapeutically, mixed manic episodes often demonstrate differential responsiveness: they are more likely to be treatment-resistant, respond more effectively to lithium than to other agents, and may benefit from certain atypical antipsychotics such as olanzapine [20,21]. These findings underscore the importance of considering mixed mania as a distinct clinical entity within bipolar disorder.

Historically, Kraepelin and Weigandt conceptualized mixed manic states in manic-depressive psychosis as combinations of manic symptoms with contrasting polar features, forming patterns such as depressive mania, ineffective mania, manic stupor, and inhibited mania [22]. While Kraepelin's typology retains theoretical relevance, it is not widely applied in contemporary clinical practice. Modern researchers describe mixed mania with terms such as “dysphoric mania,” “depressive mania,” or “mixed hypomania,” particularly when depressive symptomatology appears during acute mania [23,24].

Although expanded criteria allow the combination of manic or hypomanic episodes with subsyndromal depressive features, specific symptom constellations in mixed states remain insufficiently classified, not only in bipolar disorder type I but also in type II. Current DSM-5 guidelines enumerate competitive depressive symptoms—such as depressed mood, diminished interest, psychomotor slowing, fatigue, and recurrent thoughts of death—without offering a detailed framework for differentiating subtypes of mixed mania according to psychopathological structure. This gap underscores the need for further research to refine diagnostic and therapeutic strategies for patients with mixed manic presentations.

The purpose of the study: Determination of the pathoplastic effect of cannabioiodes on the first manic or mixed episode and potential predictors of eutymia formation.

Materials and methods. Patients diagnosed with bipolar affective disorder (BAD) were observed for a period of six months following their initial hospitalization due to a manic or mixed episode (N=47). Participants were divided into two distinct groups:

The experimental group consisted of 26 patients (17 men and 9 women) who met ICD-10 criteria for cannabinoid dependence (F12). The mean age of these patients was 26,32 years (SD = 4,35), with an average duration of cannabinoid use of 6.7 years (SD = 5,46).

The control group included 21 patients (16 men and 5 women) with bipolar affective disorder who did not use cannabinoids or other psychoactive substances. The mean age of patients in this group was 34,2 years (SD = 6.85).

The study evaluated three key domains of recovery: syndromic recovery (based on ICD-10 criteria), symptomatic recovery (assessed using the Hamilton Depression Rating Scale [HDRS-17] and the Young Mania Rating Scale [YMRS]), and functional recovery (including premorbid occupational and social status). Additionally, the duration of hospitalization, the occurrence of new affective episodes, and adherence to treatment were monitored. Results were analyzed using multifactorial statistical methods, with significance determined at $p < 0,05$.

Within the study cohort, a subgroup of patients with mixed manic episodes was identified using the following inclusion criteria:

Meeting ICD-10 criteria for one of the following categories: “Bipolar affective disorder, current episode mania without psychotic symptoms” (F31.1), “Bipolar affective disorder, current episode hypomania” (F31.0), or “Bipolar affective disorder, current mixed episode” (F31.6).

A clear predominance of manic or hypomanic features.

The presence of three or more depressive symptoms concurrently within the structure of the mixed manic state, based on validated DSM-V criteria [35].

Exclusion criteria were defined as follows:

Current substance abuse unrelated to cannabinoids.

Psychotic levels of affective disorders.

The demographic profile of the sample revealed a median age of $30,8 \pm 7,1$ years, with a predominance of female participants (63.3%), consistent with evidence suggesting greater female susceptibility to mixed manic/hypomanic states. Socioeconomic analysis indicated that most patients were socially active and well-educated: 46,2% had higher education, 30,8% had secondary specialized education, and 23,1% had completed secondary education. Marital status was distributed as 38,4% married, 34,6% single, and 26,9% divorced. Permanent employment was reported in 61,5% of participants, while 38,5% were unemployed.

Affective temperament assessment, based on anamnesis, indicated that 53,9% of patients exhibited notable temperamental traits: depressive temperaments were identified in 19,2%, and cyclothymic temperaments in 11,5%, reflecting the high prevalence of premorbid affective dysregulation among patients with mixed manic presentations.

All patients in the sample underwent comprehensive clinical-psychopathological and psychometric evaluations to quantify the severity of competing depressive symptoms. Standardized instruments included the Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (HDRS-17) and the Young Mania Rating Scale (YMRS), ensuring systematic and objective measurement of symptom intensity and severity throughout the mixed episode.

Results and discussions. In the first group of patients ($p < 0,05$), 45% were diagnosed with manic episodes accompanied by psychotic symptoms that were not limited to irritability, while 34% experienced mixed episodes in which anxiety symptoms were predominant. A six-month catamnestic follow-up revealed a significant difference in symptomatic recovery between groups: 92% of patients in the control group ($n = 26$) achieved symptomatic recovery, whereas only 37% of patients in the cannabinoid-dependent group reached similar recovery. Moreover, patients with bipolar affective disorder who did not use cannabinoids had a significantly shorter hospital stay ($p < 0,05$) and demonstrated higher treatment adherence compared to those in the first group. Functional recovery was achieved by only 35% of cannabinoid-using patients, and syndromic recovery by 53%. Within six months, 26% of the first group required hospitalization due to recurrent episodes of mania or depression (13%), and 11% progressed to a depressive stage without experiencing a period of euthymia. Notably, adherence to pharmacotherapy and refusal to use cannabinoids did not significantly affect the frequency of exacerbations, with 12% of patients in the first group experiencing relapses despite these factors.

Despite a generally elevated mood baseline, patients in the cannabinoid-dependent group reported pronounced lability in affective states, which was often accompanied by motor agitation, ideological and cognitive acceleration, frequent irritability, and an inability to regulate emotional reactions. Mood fluctuations were of high amplitude and frequently disproportionate to triggering events. The affective presentation was characterized by a combination of manic features, including irritability, aggression,

dissatisfaction, and heightened self-esteem. A distinguishing characteristic of the timic component was an elevated-excited mood with an angry or tense overlay, contrasting with the bright, euphoric presentation typical of pure mania. Externally, patients often exhibited visible tension and anxiety, rather than the “sunny” demeanor of classical manic episodes.

Behaviorally, patients displayed marked motor hyperactivity, which was often purposeless or ineffective. Hedonistic or pleasure-seeking behaviors were intensified, while cognitive processes accelerated to the point of racing thoughts, leading to scattered attention and monologic patterns in communication. The observed symptom profile aligns with the conceptualization of mixed dysphoric mania, characterized by pronounced irritability, internal tension, hostile responses to external stimuli, aggressive or disruptive behaviors, and suspiciousness. This clinical picture corresponds to the dysphoric variant of mania described in contemporary psychopathological literature.

Quantitative assessment using the MATHyS scale further confirmed the severity of these symptoms. High mean scores were observed in the following domains: psychomotor activity ($8,7 \pm 1,8$), motivational-behavioral engagement ($7,0 \pm 1,7$), and emotional reactivity ($8,3 \pm 0,4$). Within the emotional domain, specific high scores indicated elevated intensity of emotions ($9,2 \pm 1,1$), affective lability ($9,5 \pm 0,4$), sensitivity to external events ($8,9 \pm 1,0$), and overall emotional responsiveness ($9,1 \pm 0,8$). Conversely, the ideational domain displayed low average scores ($3,2 \pm 2,7$), suggesting that cognitive planning and goal-directed ideation were markedly impaired.

These findings collectively highlight that cannabinoid use in patients with bipolar affective disorder is associated with more severe affective dysregulation, pronounced mixed manic presentations, and challenges in achieving both functional and symptomatic recovery. The combination of elevated mood, irritability, dysphoria, and cognitive-motor agitation underscores the need for careful monitoring and targeted interventions in this patient population.

Conclusions. The use of cannabinoids in patients with bipolar affective disorder represents a significant risk factor for frequent recurrence of episodes, reduced adherence to pharmacological treatment, and diminished functional capacity during periods of euthymia. In this patient population, psychotic symptoms are observed more frequently within the framework of manic episodes, and these symptoms often do not respond effectively to standard therapeutic interventions.

In cases where mixed manic presentations occur, dysphoric mania is the predominant clinical picture. A detailed analysis of bipolar affective disorder in patients experiencing mixed manic states has allowed for the identification of two distinct clinical variants of the disease. The first variant is characterized by single or irregularly occurring, well-defined mixed manic episodes, which appear either periodically or sporadically. These episodes frequently intersect with depressive or mixed depressive phases that remain dominant throughout the course of the disorder, interspersed with relatively long periods of remission. This variant is generally associated with a more favorable prognosis.

The second variant is distinguished by regular, recurrent mixed manic episodes, often overlapping with consecutive affective phases-predominantly manic-without clearly defined periods of remission, resulting in a continuous and unfavorable course. Clinical observations indicate that patients with cycloid temperaments, as well as those presenting with dysphoric-type mixed mania, are more likely to experience this persistent and adverse pattern of bipolar affective disorder. These factors can serve as important predictors of disease severity, course chronicity, and overall prognosis.

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